

Research

The Role and Impact of NGOs in Battered Woman Syndrome Cases : A Case Study of Bangladesh

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Abstract : This study examines the events of domestic violence and Battered Woman Syndrome (BWS), the role and influence of NGOs in BWS issues from around the world and specifically focusing on Bangladesh. Detailed research studies show that, these effects can vary depending on cultural and regulatory conditions. In a subsequent study, the impact of women's status on violence is highly contextual, as it depends on the degree of cultural conservatism in the region. Currently, expert testimony should explain the consequences of abuse in each case due to widespread misunderstandings and misconceptions regarding domestic violence victims in Bangladesh. Many other non-governmental organizations have adopted the grassroots approach and have established a village-level development program for the immediate need of women, as well as long-term approval. Our study shows that NGOs play a positive and important role in preventing abuses of women, which is a common phenomenon in Bangladesh, and need changes in women's protection legislation to prevent domestic violence. Bangladesh's effective non-governmental violence prevention (BWS) strategies should be incorporated both publicly through information campaigns and advertising, as well as through a community network.

Keyword: BWS, Bangladesh, NGOs, violence, women's movement.

Introduction:

Battered woman syndrome (BWS) is a psychological situation and express a pattern of behavior that develops in victims of domestic violent behavior as a effect of victims, prolonged violent behavior, Where the victim gets depressed, defeated again and disable said that her abuser is not able to leave. To be familiar with 'battered woman's syndrome' we must know about that how the

victim become a battered woman. According to various experts on battered women, a woman should experience at least two cycles before they can be labeled, in an illegal defense assessment as a "battered woman." The 1st one is Tension Build Phase, where the women engaged in relationship which create tension in relationship the 2nd phase is Physiological and emotion stage, the most important and significant in BWS where the abuser expected from abuse some emotional damages, hurtful accident, like Physical, Sexual, Emotional and Psychological. The third phase is Honeymoon Stage, this phase is constant for Battered women and very distractive for victim because in this phase the abuser tries to fix his wrongdoing and apologizes and during the honeymoon phase, the abuser is forgiven, and the cycle begins again.

The study aims to analyze the role and impacts of NGOs in cases of BWS and the issues resulting in it specifically related to Bangladesh. The principle of multiple victim syndrome, "Battered Woman Syndrome", uses "cycle of violence" and "conscience helplessness" to describe the development of psychological problems in women who are subjected to constant violence by their husbands. Later, a battered woman's syndrome entered the legal realm when Walker began testifying about BWS (Battered Woman's Syndrome) in a trial of women accused of killing her abuser. And the risk of contracting the human immune deficiency virus (HIV). Unfortunately, domestic violence has never been considered a serious public health problem in Bangladesh. Therefore, it has never received much attention at the policy level or in planning health research frameworks and studies. Therefore, despite the recognition that violence can have serious implications for women's reproductive health, our understanding of the relationship between these two aspects is limited. Despite the growing number of well-documented literature on the prevalence of domestic violence against women, very few studies in Bangladesh have focused on the health effects of women.

Battered Woman Syndrome came up as a theory in the 1970's when a prominent Psychologist, (Dr. Lenore Walker) tried to explain the psycho-social condition of a woman suffering from domestic violence in her book "The Battered Woman". Spousal violence is common and results in costly problems both for society and for the reproductive health of women. Despite the recognition that violence may be associated with serious consequences for women's reproductive health, our understanding of the relationship between the two remains limited. In this paper I explained that NGOs, as one of the most visible sets of actors in the related fields of human development and human rights, can play a significant role in helping to achieve BWS. NGOs are especially well

suited to action for BWS because of their size and reach, closeness to local populations, willingness to confront the *status quo*, and ability to address transnational threats through coalition-building. While NGOs face many obstacles in reorienting their activities explicitly towards BWS.

Literature Review:

According to this study (Walker, 1979; Barnes, 1999; Beven, 2002; Dutton, 2000; Gerbert, 1996), Domestic violence has a long research history. Through this extensive history, academicians have developed theories that attempt to explain this phenomenon. One theory that integrates the victim's culture, ethnicity, and familial background to help explain the experience of domestic violence. A strong need exists for such a theory; a culturally sensitive theory of domestic violence; one that takes the first hand perspective of the victim and tries to understand and explain the phenomenon through a cultural and ethnic context. It is clear that one's culture certainly helps in defining the meanings that one gives to various experiences in life; however, what is not known is what role culture and ethnicity have in the development of the meanings that one gives to being a victim of this phenomenon.

Spousal violence was significantly higher amongst the group of less educated women who had been in several marriages; indicating that the social and behavioral traits of women act as catalysts for spousal violence. Abusive husbands also had been married several times and were more likely to be addicted to alcohol or drugs.

This demonstrates that the behavioral traits of husbands were also responsible for spousal violence. Spousal violence injuries adversely affect the health and well-being of women. More than three-quarters of physically violated women suffered injuries as a result of this violence. About 50% of these injuries were minor and about 10% serious. Sexual violence adversely affected women's health; more than 80% of sexually violated women complained of pelvic pain, more than 50% reported reproductive tract infections, and more than 50% reported symptoms of irritable bowel syndrome. Abused women suffered from gynecological problems at the time of pregnancy significantly more than non-abused women and abused women suffered from reproductive tract infections significantly more than non-abused women. Abusive husbands suffered from sexually transmitted diseases (STD) significantly more than non-abusive husbands. Abused women used contraception significantly less than non-abused women. Logistic regression analysis suggested that spousal violence was the most important contributing factor for reproductive health problems in women .

Domestic violence against women exists in every society, ranging from low income countries to the highly developed ones. (Jayaraman, 2004) reports that, at least one-third of all women have experienced domestic violence (by their husbands/family members) in their lifetime. According to the incidence of domestic violence in Bangladesh has also been demonstrated in a number of studies. There is a study stated that, 47 per cent of their productive-aged women in rural Bangladesh were physically abused (Schuler et al, 1996). While considering two rural areas in separate districts, found the rate of domestic violence around 42 per cent (Koenig et al. (2003). 66 per cent of the rural married women were physically abused (slapped/pushed/hit) regularly during their married life, whereas 33 percent were kicked/burned/hit by sticks (Bates et al. (2004). Domestic violence also contributed markedly to the maternal mortality in Bangladesh (Fauveau et al. (1988) and Ronsmans and Khat (1999).

According to (Kim and Cho 1992; Jejeebhoy and Cook 1997; Martin et al. 1999; Hoffman et al. 1994, Mahajan 1990).

Domestic violence has been linked to individual, household and demographic characteristics, socio-economic status, adverse reproductive health outcomes, contextual considerations, etc.

A number of studies revealed strong negative relations between the risk of domestic violence and household wealth and husband's education. According to some other studies, such as; Higher age (Kim and Cho 1992; Schuler et al. 1996), higher number of children (Schuler et al. 1996; Rao 1997) and woman's education (Schuler et al. 1996; Jewkes et al. 2002) are also found to reduce the risk of violence.

(Koenig et al. (2003) stated that A survey of women of reproductive age in rural Uganda, found male partners' alcohol consumption and their perceived HIV risk as being two important factors of domestic violence against females.

Some other studies (van der Straten et al. 1998; Watts et al. 1998; Rao 1997; Jewkes et al. 2002) also recognized a strong relationship between alcohol/drug consumption and domestic violence while others (van der Straten et al. 1998; Maman et al. 2000; Coker and Richter 1998) explored the link between HIV status and domestic violence.

In Bangladesh, several attempts were made to explain domestic violence. Bates et al (2004), using data from six rural areas in three districts, the role of women's education, their participation in micro-credit lending programs, contribution to household spending, dowry organization and marriage. To examine the registration of women as a potential factor in women's rights. And

weakness in marriage. In men's education, it was found that the chances of violence decreased significantly. The dowry agreement or personal income (more than the nominal contribution to the family) increased the likelihood of violence. Based on a cross-examination of reproductive age women, (Koenig et al. Oh god (1999) point to the important role played by women's social and individual factors, such as women's status and independence. Studies show that once again, these effects can vary depending on cultural and regulatory conditions. In a subsequent study, Koenig et al. (2003) found that the impact of women's status on violence is highly contextual, as it depends on the degree of cultural conservatism in the region.

Historical Perspectives on Violence against Women

In colonial times, a husband realized because his family was in charge of his property, including his wife. The legal rights of a wife can be combined with those of her husband and he can be held liable for his vicious acts. As the owner of his house, the husband had the power to punish his wife, provided he did not impose a permanent injury. According to this credible tradition, in 1824 the Mississippi Supreme Court ruled in *Bradley v. State*, where Bradley's court ruled that husbands had the right to exercise restricted punishment against their wives. Fortunately for women, Bradley claimed excellence in *Harris vs. State* after seventy years, where the Mississippi Supreme Court pressured *Bradley vs. State* to collide down.

Calvin Bradley v. State (Mississippi) enforced the first US lawsuit "Reasonable punishment." In case 120, the court ruled that Bradley, convicted in the lower court for stabbing and mistreating his wife, had gone too far in punishing his wife. Harris was convicted in the aggression and trial court with a report that determined to kill his wife. The incident showed that he stabbed his wife and hit him with a heavy stick on the board. He made a strong appeal to his conviction that no evidence was presented here to prosecute the murder. The appellate court agreed and withdrew its sentence and referred the case to new proceedings. The state appealed and the Mississippi Supreme Court reversed the case.

Although it was eliminated from the acceptance of judicial sanctions, it has begun to see domestic violence under the customary law of family privacy, which proves that non-interference in marital relations is justified. The court was not on its way to abolishing detention without initiating punishment for activities related to intimate violence. During this time, the courts have often consisted only of minorities, such as African-American and indigenous immigrants, Caucasian middle- and upper-class men as privileged.

Middle- and upper-class men accused of intimate violence use court protection as a means to educate abusive women about the use of advanced homegrown traditions to prevent murderous spouses. This era of "social service" encouraged women to confess their share of guilt for inciting violence and encouraged them to stay with their husbands and change their habits so that they could become better wives.

This idea and the long-publicized doctrine of family secrecy led to the elimination of the problem of male violence. This period continued in court until the end of the 20th century.

Women's Rights Movement (1960)

The women's rights movement in the 1960s sought to focus on the unequal role of domestic violence and spouses. Rights activists and activists decided to focus on self-affirmation of crimes related to their natural aggression. This emphasis on domestic inequality has led to the rise of women's hate movement. The first defenders of backward women documented that the law would be an important tool to protect them from violence.

The first publication of this movement is the failure of police officers to protect women from attacks. Police departments in the United States look at smuggled women and often refuse to intervene in domestic violence situations. In the early 1970s, a class action lawsuit was filed against the Police Department in New York and Auckland, California.

The first shelter for injured women in the United States was established in 1977 in St. Paul, Minnesota. Countless victims' advocacy programs have been created and professional literature on the subject, and many medical and law schools have incorporated curricula that focus on domestic violence and its consequences.

Overview of violence in Bangladesh

Violence against women has been defined as "any act of gender-based violence that can cause physical, sexual or psychological harm to women, including freedom from such actions, coercion or liberty. But also, the risk of deprivation, whether in public life. " In this case in 1993, both men and women face violence in one way or another, but not before a significant percentage of victims of violence that threaten life from middle to old age Further, postpartum lives are missing out on opportunities for postpartum violence and child labor to survive as early as possible. Marriages, child prostitution, sexual abuse and other victims. Even in their own homes, women are not protected. In fact, they may be at greater risk of domestic violence than anywhere else. Domestic violence usually involves violent and controlling behaviors that can lead to many forms of physical

abuse such as beatings, slaps, beatings, beatings, and mental abuse. The immediate and growing health effects of violence on women range from fatal to non-fatal consequences. The fatal consequences are murder, suicide, maternal mortality and AIDS deaths. Non-fatal outcomes, including permanent disability, unwanted and complicated pregnancy, HIV and other genetic infections (STIS), depression, anxiety, chronic pain syndrome, suicidal thoughts and more.

According to the Bangladesh National Women Lawyers Association (BNWLA) on violence against women, in Bangladesh there were 530 domestic violence cases, 370 abuses, 327 suicides, 140 cases of suicide, 140 abductions, 122 abductions. Incidence, 146 cases of unnatural deaths recorded are vague, but speculation is high. (Violence Against Women in Bangladesh (January to December 2001))

Role of NGOs in Battered Women Syndrome

NGOs generally work with women's organizations such as BNWLA, Nirpokhoko. Government agencies include the Ministry of Health and Family Welfare, the Ministry of Information, the Ministry of Children and Women's Affairs, the Ministry of Social Welfare and the Ministry of Interior. NGOs and GIOs work with various preventive measures to raise awareness, education, counseling, courts and divorce proceedings, and to reintegrate survivors into society on issues of child welfare. NGOs provide advisory services to volunteer Naripokho counselors. The social welfare department provides clothing, financial support. BNWLA offers legal advice and temporary shelter.

This Non- Government Organizations (NGOs) is different in size and scope. Some women's rights organizations are involved in political activism, such as raising awareness and promoting promotion. Some NGOs have focused on economic development through micro programmers. Many other non-governmental organizations have adopted the grassroots approach and have established a village-level development program for the immediate need of women, as well as long-term approval. In addition to the general emphasis on women's participation, many NGOs seek to strengthen women's social position on issues such as dowry, marriage registration, violence against women and access to legal remedies. In addition to their participation in broad-spectrum NGO programmers, women have also concentrated on several specialized organizations, especially focusing on their social, legal and democratic rights.

As a result of this initiative, information was also collected on the type and type of incidents (such as acid attack, rape, murder, physical abuse, dowry, child marriage, family feud, suicide, and

hilarious marriage) (for example, court cases by DLAC, BRAC). Legal advice and assistance by, Using by UP, etc. From September 2012 to May 25, a total of 5 incidents from 5 unions were reported and included in the pilot database.

Working through the program allows members to have direct access, many of whom have suffered various forms of violence in their lives. As part of the BRAC Community Empowerment Program, 8% (25,638) members received training, including medical assistance, counseling and rehabilitation. They were also made aware of their rights in Bangladesh law, and common cultural practices such as beatings or early marriage are also illegal. More than 23,800 members of REPA WCG received a direct line number and a direct service line with a related help line number and information immediately available in the face of violence. As a result of their participation in training, women become aware of issues such as gender discrimination; Concepts, categories and factors of violence against women; Measures to prevent and protect violence; And relevant laws. A positive result of the training was that 90% of the participants realized that women must be free from these injustices to fully enjoy their rights and participate effectively in society. Upon receiving the training, WCG members reported that they had more confidence to strengthen their rights.

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Battered women's syndrome was not allowed to participate unless a decision was made about Ahluwalia. In addition to being the first English case to recognize traumatic female syndrome, Ahluwalia's decision is also crucial to properly altering the "duplicate" need for provocation. The court indicated that the delay would not interfere with the use of provocative self-control, but that the delay would increase the likelihood of its rejection as a warning.

The decision of the widow to protect women from beating was also important, as they influenced the demand for "rationality." The court ruled that in view of the need for self-defense and provocation, the psychological characteristics of a woman who had been implicated in expert testimony about a woman's syndrome could be useful to judges. Therefore, the jury was given the opportunity to consider the consequences of prolonged corruption, which refers to the meaning of a reasonable person. Another consequence of this national decision is that the system of self-defense and incitement can now be used instead of responsible responsibilities that have not been used before due to difficulty meeting security needs.

After the criminal court sentenced her to life imprisonment, the appeals court found Ms. Ahluwalia guilty of "insecure" and "unsatisfactory" and ordered a trial for her lack of responsibility. Here she received a request for murder and was sentenced to 40 months in prison, just before serving a sentence at any time.

Therefore, for the first time in a lawsuit, a woman jumped on board as evidence of the legal relevance of the psychological impact of the emotional state of being in an adverse relationship with her husband.

Almost 30 years after Ahluwalia murdered her abusive husband and three courts in the customary law country regularly accepted the defense of the bruised woman, Jibonnahar, a Bangladeshi woman's lifeguard took her abusive husband's life in January 2019. So far, her story is what described her to the police and was published in the newspaper.

Jibonnahar, a garment worker, was married for five years. During the marriage she was subjected to domestic violence at the hands of her husband. She asked for money that day. He was angry at his refusal and hit her with a brick. Later that night, while he was sleeping, she used the same brick to hit him several times and was subsequently killed by breathing. The next day she went to work. When she returned home at night, she cut his body into pieces and threw it into the sack. Then she carried the bags and placed them in nearby places, where they were readily available.

Jibonnahar did not try to escape justice. After her arrest, she was paraded before the press with bare feet. Her video interview with the police was put in the public domain. The local police superintendent wasted no time in holding a press conference declaring the murder a "murder confession." The media showed no mercy when the news spread. Over the years, no one made any connection to his mental state (which was indicated by her in police interview) due to torture and the incident.

There is a strange similarity between the Ahluwalia case and the case of Jibonnahar. As things stand, their reactions are against them. If any women's rights organization accepts her case and presents a fair defense, just like the Black Sisters of South hall did to Ahluwalia in 1992, that could change.

CONCLUSION

Battered Woman Syndrome has made it clear that the murder of abusive spouses by their injured partner is a legal system failure to provide such unpleasant partner protection from their abusive partners. One way to overcome this national failure is to create a law that addresses not only the

problems of women in conflict, but must also be abuse-proof so that they can adequately address the concerns raised by Meir Dan-Cohen. In addition, the Canadian approach to the problem, which considers battered female syndrome as a mental state that a "normal" woman can possess, must be taken into account.

All these concerns must be addressed in the Model Law and a new kind of protective self-defense of Battered Woman Syndrome must be formulated. This defense will include a complete subjective standard of rationality, and will examine the circumstances in which the defendant was committed, which requires a certain degree of model law. The standard of proof will include that a defendant provides sufficient evidence that he or she was subjected to a substantial battery incident and that his sudden escalation, which could result in serious harm to himself, could guarantee an act such as murder. The expert testimony of a mental health professional also testified that the accused showed an honest belief in serious harm. And, more importantly, a systematic rejection of retrospective theory based on Seligman's research and Walker's conclusions about "learned helplessness."

While there seems to be no clear answer to the horizon, victims of domestic violence who face murder as a way to protect their abuser face considerable criminal liability problems. Detailed studies of the long-term effects of abusive abuse of the women's movement require reliable scientific research. A psychologist with educational, scientific or specialized knowledge of the effects of battering describes the complexity of the psychological process of the transfer flow.

Joining hands with the cycle of violence that affects women. Since the defendant is accused of domestic violence and he or she is accused of killing the abuser, it may be necessary to redefine the value of a reasonable person in the murder. Otherwise, fact-seekers will have to fight endlessly to understand how a reasonable person should apply values to information beyond the perception of the ordinary rational person.

This proposed reform will address many of the important problems currently associated with women's self-defense claims. Many of the experts mentioned above and the investigator believe that the current sources of criminal codes are sufficiently well equipped to face the situation of battered women.

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Dedication

Not mentioned.

Conflicts of Interest

There are no conflicts to declare.

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